

The ratio of the Ag^{103} activities obtained at 60 Mev from enriched and normal cadmium, calculated to the end of bombardment and corrected for the difference in target material, was found to be 20 to 1 as compared with an enrichment factor of 27. The cyclotron beam was not monitored but the intensity was approximately the same. Thus, the 1.1 hour-activity is produced from Cd^{106} and a (p, α) reaction to produce Ag^{103} is suggested.

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QUANTITATIVE ISOLATION OF DL-GLUTAMIC ACID FROM A
MIXTURE OF DL-2-PYRROLIDONE-5-CARBOXYLIC ACID
AND DL-GLUTAMYLGLUTAMIC ACID

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When glutamic acid is isolated from a protein by acid hydrolysis, it is generally assumed that glutamic acid is present in the protein as a straight-chain peptide. During this investigation it is shown that a quantitative yield of DL-glutamic acid is obtained when a mixture of DL-2-pyrrolidone-5-carboxylic acid and the dipeptide DL-glutamylglutamic acid is hydrolysed by hydrochloric acid. This suggests that in a natural protein glutamic acid may be present as a linear peptide as well as a peptide of 2-pyrrolidone-6-carboxylic acid (the cyclic analogue).

A mixture of 129 mg. of DL-2-pyrrolidone-5-carboxylic acid and 276 mg. of DL-glutamylglutamic acid and 25 c.c. of 6N-HCl was refluxed on a water-bath for 16 hours. It was then evaporated in vacuum when 541 mg. of a yellowish white crystalline material was obtained. Twice crystallisation of this from distilled water under reduced pressure in a desiccator gave 538 mg. of colorless prismatic crystals, m.p. 196°. (Found: N, 7.56. Calc: N, 7.63%). Its mixed m.p. with a genuine sample of DL-glutamic acid hydrochloride was also 196°. Its R_f value was also identical with that of genuine glutamic acid hydrochloride.

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